

Potentiometric and Visible Spectral Studies of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Nickel(II) containing 1,2-Diaminopropane and some Amino Acids

M. SIVASANKARAN NAIR*^a, P. THILLAI ARASU^a, M. A. NEELAKANTAN^b, M. VINCENT^c and M. SANKARANARAYANA PILLAI^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, M. S. University, Abhishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627 012

^bDepartment of Chemistry, National Engineering College, Nalattinuputhur-627 716

^cDepartment of Chemistry, S. T. Hindu College, Nagercoil-629 002

Manuscript received 6 March 1995, revised 26 September 1996, accepted 8 February 1997

In biological systems transition metal ions exist predominantly in the form of different mixed ligand complexes and hence, investigations on the stability of mixed ligand complexes in relation with various structural features are increasingly becoming more important¹⁻⁴. This type of study will help towards understanding the driving forces that lead to the formation of such complexes in biological systems. Here, we report a systematic pH-metric and visible absorption studies on the formation and stability of mixed-ligand complexes of Ni^{II} containing 1,2-diaminopropane (dp) and four amino acids, viz. DL-2-aminobutyric acid (2-aba), DL-3-aminobutyric acid (3-aba), 4-aminobutyric acid (4-aba) and DL-4-amino-3-hydroxybutyric acid (abha) at 37° and *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ Na(ClO₄).

Results and Discussion

The computer-based analysis of the pH-titration data showed the presence of the ternary species of the types NiABH, NiAB, NiA₂BH and NiA₂B in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba(B) system, NiABH, NiAB and NiA₂BH complexes in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-3-aba/4-aba(B) systems, and NiAB type of species in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-abha(B) system.

The log K_{NiAB}^{NiA} and log K_{NiAB}^{NiB} values (Table 2) in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-amino acid (B) systems are comparable to the respective log β_{NiB} and log β_{NiA} values (Table 1) after

primary ligand binds the metal in a bidentate manner resulting in a five-membered ring and the secondary ligands 2-aba, 2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba bind Ni^{II} through its hard oxygen and relatively soft nitrogen forming five-, six- and seven-membered rings respectively. The log K_{NiAB}^{NiA} value (8.37) computed in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-abha(B) system is comparable to the log β_{NiB} value (8.47) in the Ni^{II}-abha(B) system⁵ demonstrating the tridentate binding of abha in its NiAB ternary species. The $\Delta \log K_{NiAB}$ (= log $\beta_{NiAB} - \log \beta_{NiB} - \log \beta_{NiA}$) value (1.24) in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-3-aba(B) system is more positive compared to that of 0.02 and -0.12 respectively in the 2-aba and 4-aba secondary ligand systems. This demonstrates higher stability for the Ni^{II} chelates containing five- and six-membered rings compared to that for the five-five or five-seven membered chelates. The same trend has also been reflected in the log X_{NiAB} (= 2 log $\beta_{NiAB} - \log \beta_{NiA_2} - \log \beta_{NiB_2}$) parameter, where the value obtained is maximum in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-3-aba(B) system compared to that in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba system (Table 2). The formation of NiA₂B type of species in the

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba, 3-aba, 4-aba AND abha(B) SYSTEMS

Temp. = 37°, *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³

Parameter	2-aba	3-aba	4-aba	abha
log β_{NiABH}	19.80(4)	20.39(2)	20.54(4)	—
log β_{NiAB}	12.49(7)	12.26(9)	10.03(9)	15.32(9)
log β_{NiA_2BH}	26.87(3)	27.48(3)	28.35(6)	—
log β_{NiA_2B}	18.50(9)	—	—	—
pK_{NiABH}^H	7.31	8.13	10.51	—
log K_{NiAB}^{NiA}	5.54	5.31	—	8.37
log K_{NiAB}^{NiB}	6.93	8.19	6.83	6.85
$\Delta \log K_{NiAB}$	-0.02	1.24	-0.12	-0.10
log X_{NiAB}	1.97	3.46	—	1.40
log $K_{NiA_2B}^{NiA_2}$	5.43	—	—	—
log $K_{NiA_2B}^{NiAB}$	6.01	—	—	—

Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba(B) system is not surprising because in this species Ni^{II} can attain the preferred coordination number

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR THE PROTON AND Ni^{II} COMPLEXES OF 2-aba, 3-aba, 4-aba AND abha BINARY SYSTEMS

Temp. = 37°, *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	2-aba ^a	3-aba ^a	4-aba ^a	abha ^b
log β_{HB}	9.43(1)	9.95(1)	10.15(1)	12.88(11)
log β_{H_2B}	11.54(1)	11.30(1)	14.24(1)	21.91(2)
log β_{H_3B}	—	—	—	25.78(2)
log β_{NiB}	5.56(4)	4.07(5)	3.20(6)	8.47(8)
log β_{NiB_2}	9.94(6)	7.99(8)	—	16.17(5)
log $K_{NiB_2}^{NiB}$	4.38	3.92	—	7.70

^aRef. 5. ^bRef. 6.

giving allowance for the statistical considerations. This suggests that in the NiAB ternary species the binding modes of the ligands A and B are similar to that in the corresponding binary species. Thus in the NiAB species, the dp pri-

of six due to the bidentate binding of two dp primary ligands and one 2-aba(B) ligand. The non-detection of this type of species in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-3-aba/4-aba/ahba(B) systems may probably be accounted by considering steric factors.

By considering the fact that protonated binary complexes have been detected only in the Ni^{II}-dp(A) system and not in the Ni^{II}-2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba binary systems (Table 1), it can be expected that in the NiABH species in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba(B) systems the extra proton resides with the dp primary ligand. However, the trends in the pK_{NiABH}^H value (Table 2) follow the trends in $\log \beta_{HB}$ values for the 2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba secondary ligands⁶. This demonstrates that the extra proton in the NiABH species in these systems resides in the secondary ligand probably with their amino groups. Similar trends have also been reported in a number of Ni^{II} ternary systems containing 2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba secondary ligands⁶. The trends in the $\log \beta_{NiA_2BH}$ values in these three systems follow the trends of $\log \beta_{NiABH}$ values demonstrating the site of protonation in the NiA₂BH species to be the secondary ligand.

The species distribution diagrams have been obtained for all the ternary systems and the ternary complexes have been found to be in appreciable amounts. In order to demon-

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba(B) ternary system at $C_M = 0.003$, $C_A = C_B = 0.006$: (1) unbound Ni^{II}, (2) NiAH, (3) NiABH, (4) NiAB, (5) NiA₂BH and (6) NiA₂B. Curves for the NiA, NiA₂H, NiA₃, NiB and NiB₂ could not be drawn due to their very low concentrations.

strate this trend, the diagram for the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba(B) system is given in Fig. 1.

The visible absorption spectra obtained⁷ in the Ni^{II}-dp, 2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba binary systems contain only two peaks and the third band might have been obscured due to the strong charge transfer bands (Table 3). The λ_{max} values (Table 3) for the NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba(B) systems follow the same trend as those

TABLE 3—ABSORPTION MAXIMUM VALUES (nm) FOR Ni^{II} COMPLEXES OF dp(A), 2-aba, 3-aba, 4-aba AND ahba(B) BINARY SYSTEMS AND THE CORRESPONDING TERNARY SYSTEMS

Species	Binary systems (B)				
	dp*	2-aba*	3-aba*	4-aba*	ahba*
NiB	606	643	654	719	655
	365	383	389	392	390
NiB ₂	575	627	650	—	647
	353	375	385	—	384
	Ternary systems				
		2-aba	3-aba	4-aba	ahba
NiAB		600	615	618	614
		362	368	369	368

*Ref. 7.

obtained for the NiB and NiB₂ species in the Ni^{II}-2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba(B) binary systems. That is, the λ_{max} value for the NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba(B) systems (Table 3) decreases in the secondary ligand with the order: 4-aba > 3-aba > 2-aba. Thus the ligand field strength for 2-aba, 3-aba and 4-aba ligands found in their respective Ni^{II} binary complexes has also been maintained in the Ni^{II} ternary systems in the presence of dp primary ligand. In the Ni^{II}-dp(A)-ahba(B) system also the λ_{max} value obtained for NiAB species can probably be accounted by considering the formation of two 5- and one 6-membered chelates.

Experimental

All the ligands were obtained from Fluka. Ni(ClO₄)₂ and other reagents were prepared and estimated as described earlier². The experimental procedure for the pH-metric studies has also been described earlier². The auxiliary data for the binary systems of Ni^{II} with ligands A and B under the same experimental conditions were taken from the literature^{5,6}. All the calculations were done with the aid of the computer program⁸ MINIQUAD-75 using a HCl Magnum II computer. The species distribution plots were drawn with the aid of AUTO PLOT computer program⁹ using a HCl Oasys III computer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 3b spectrophotometer using PECSS software. For recording the spectra, 1 : 1 : 1 metal-ligand(A)-ligand(B) solutions were used at a particular pH were NiAB mixed-ligand species had maximum concentration as evidenced by the species distribution plots.

NOTE

References

1. "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", ed. H. SIGEL, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1971-1994, Vols.1-30.
2. M. S. NAIR, P. T. ARASU, M. S. PILLAI and C. NATARAJAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 917.
3. M. S. NAIR, P. T. ARASU, M. S. PILLAI and C. NATARAJAN, *Talanta*, 1993, **40**, 1411.
4. M. S. NAIR, P. T. ARASU, P. THILAGAVATHI and M. A. NEELAKANTAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 429.
5. M. S. NAIR, P. T. ARASU, T. L. FERANDO, M. S. PILLAI and M. CHANDRAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 807.
6. P. T. ARASU, Ph.D. Thesis, M. S. University, 1993.
7. M. S. NAIR, unpublished results.
8. P. GANS, A. VACCA and A. SABATINI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.
9. M. S. NAIR and M. A. NEELAKANTAN, unpublished work.